

**The Roles of Selected Stakeholders in Effective Communication Usage for Insecurity
Reduction in Ekiti State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

Background

Understanding the roles of diverse stakeholders is paramount in the pursuit of safer communities. This is because of indiscriminate unrest orchestrated by insurgents in present-day Nigeria.

Objectives

This study examines the roles of effective communication among stakeholders like government agencies, law enforcement authorities, and civil society organizations (CSOs) in reducing insecurity in Oye Ekiti.

Methodology

Three investigative questions guided the study. The study adopted a quantitative research design. Data gathered through an instrument titled Stakeholders Participation in Communication Usage for Insecurity Reduction (SPCUIR) was analysed to discern stakeholder perceptions and contributions.

Results

The findings highlight that government agencies are seen as active implementers and policy developers, law enforcement authorities play crucial response and collaboration roles, and CSOs advocate for transparency and actively contribute to security measures with the help of communication gadgets.

Conclusion

The distinct roles of stakeholders in communication usage coalesce to form concerted efforts aimed at reducing insecurity in Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti state, Nigeria.

Unique Contributions

The study contributes to the understanding of stakeholder dynamics in using communication to enhance community security.

Key Recommendations

Recommendations include enhancing collaboration, community engagement, transparency, and capacity-building initiatives. While the study provides valuable insights, limitations in the scope and reliance on perceptions are acknowledged.

Keywords: Stakeholders, Participation, Communication usage, Insecurity reduction, law enforcement, government, leaders.

Introduction

Insecurity is a pervasive challenge that affects the well-being and development of communities worldwide. Ekiti State, located in Nigeria, is no exception to this issue. The state has experienced various forms of insecurity, including crime, violence, and conflicts (Nasiru, 2020; Akinola & Liaga, 2023). The consequences of insecurity are far-reaching, impacting the economy, social cohesion, and overall well-being of Nigerian citizens. Addressing this complex issue requires a comprehensive approach involving the active participation of various stakeholders.

Stakeholders are individuals, groups, or organizations that have a vested interest in or are affected by a particular issue, such as insecurity (Benn et al., 2016). In the context of reducing insecurity, stakeholders can include government agencies, law enforcement authorities, community leaders, civil society organizations, local businesses, educational institutions, religious groups, residents, and affected communities. Stakeholder participation in communication usage for the

reduction of insecurity is a critical approach that involves engaging various stakeholders in collaborative efforts to address security challenges. By involving key actors and fostering effective communication strategies, it becomes possible to create a safer and more secure environment (Shannon, 2018; Olajiga et al., 2024).

The roles of Stakeholders in the reduction of insecurity include collaboration and coordination of efforts. Stakeholders' participation enables this among different entities involved in security efforts by bringing together diverse perspectives and expertise. Stakeholders can pool resources, share information, and coordinate strategies to address security challenges effectively (Nwabueze & Mileski, 2018; Francis, et al., 2023). Another significant role is local knowledge and insights; community members and local leaders possess valuable knowledge and insights about the specific security issues and dynamics within their areas, engaging them as stakeholders allows for the incorporation of local perspectives, which can lead to more contextually relevant and effective security solutions. Stakeholders' active participation can enhance early warning systems by encouraging community members to report suspicious activities and security threats promptly this timely information can assist security agencies in taking proactive measures to prevent incidents or respond effectively (Robert et al., 2020).

Stakeholders' involvement in insecurity reduction efforts helps mobilize financial and non-financial resources to support security initiatives. This can include funding, personnel, infrastructure, technology, and community support, contributing to the overall effectiveness of security measures (Cornelissen, 2017). Involving stakeholders in insecurity reduction can also include community engagement and ownership. This fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility within the community. When individuals and groups feel invested in security efforts, they are more likely to actively participate, support initiatives, and take collective action to promote safety. Other roles can also include trust and confidence, social cohesion and resilience, policy development and implementation, evaluation and feedback, etc.

As primary stakeholders, government agencies are responsible for formulating and implementing security policies. Omoroje et al. (2020) discovered that government agencies actively participate in implementing security measures to reduce insecurity. Omoroje et al. add that the effectiveness of the security agents in performing their statutory responsibilities with patriotism comes from the true formulation, execution, and implementation of security policies and will reduce contemporary security challenges in the country. In addition to government efforts, Abdullahi (2020) observed that little collaboration from other agencies, which includes, which includes NGOs, civil societies, conventional rulers and different safety organizations, performed a full-size role. Aliyu (2023) has unveiled that an effective information security strategy would be the best measure to adopt by government agencies to tackle the insecurity challenges faced by Nigeria which also obstructs its potential to drive sustainable national security and development. Effective communication among different government departments and agencies fosters a coordinated response to security threats. Communication, according to Brahmaiah and Demudu (2016), is the transfer of information from one character to another. However, the statistics transferred need to be comprehensible to the receiver. For example, conversation is made by someone to another person to discuss something or deliver a message from the communicator to the communicant. Radhika (2020) said that communication is a process in which a message is delivered to a recipient or more to change their behaviour. Radhika (2020) argues that communication is delivering an intentional message to the recipient to influence the recipient's behaviour. The above definitions are backed up by Kunnu et al. (2018), who emphasize the significance of inter-agency communication in improving security outcomes. These researchers unveiled that regular meetings and information sharing between agencies enhance intelligence gathering and crisis response capabilities. Examples are the Federal inland Revenue Service, Nigerian Communication Commission, Federal Ministry of Finance, Board of Internal Revenue, and public complaints commission.

Law enforcement authorities are at the forefront of combating insecurity. Timely and accurate communication is essential for operational success. The research of Akinlabi and Okedara (2019) highlights the importance of technology in facilitating communication among law enforcement personnel. Obarisiagbon and Akintoye (2019) noted that law enforcement authorities effectively respond to security incidents and emergencies. Smith and Johnson (2018) posit that law enforcement authorities actively engage with communities to build strong relationships, especially in the usage of mobile communication systems and foster a sense of security. This suggests that mobile communication systems and real-time updates enable swift reactions to criminal activities, leading to improved security conditions. Examples are the Nigeria customs service, Nigeria Security and Civil Defense Forces, Federal road safety corps, Peace Corps, Nigerian police corps, and Nigeria Prison Service.

Civil society plays a vital role in promoting transparency and accountability in security matters. Their communication strategies, such as public awareness campaigns and advocacy efforts, help raise awareness about security challenges and potential solutions. A study by Onifade et al. (2019) highlights how CSOs can bridge the communication gap between the government and the citizens, facilitating more effective security measures. Examples are cooperative and collective, online groups and social media societies, unions, nongovernmental organizations, and nonprofits (Omede & Bakare, 2014; Muhammad & Abdulkarim, 2017; Popoola & Alao, 2017; Oyekunle, 2024). The findings of Osayekemwen and Adeoluwa (2022) show that Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) provide platforms and opportunities for public participation and input in security-related decision-making processes. Effective communication, according to Morolake (2017), minimizes the threats to national security, promoting peace as effective communication is aimed at ensuring peace and security among all the stakeholders in a nation, including citizens, media, other institutions and the government. Whatever is spread in the media usually influences communication among various institutions in the nation, including the family, educational institutions, religious groups and organizations. Therefore, the stakeholders of a nation must pay attention to the way they handle information and quell crises with their communication strategies. This suggests that the issue of security threats should not be one man's business but all-encompassing, including educational institutions.

Educational institutions can play a significant role in enhancing security awareness among students and staff. By implementing communication strategies that promote safety and security, educational institutions contribute to the community's overall well-being. A study by Adewuyi and Ojo (2019) explores the impact of security-oriented communication in educational settings. Examples are schools, colleges, universities, or training centres.

Religious groups have a broad reach in communities and can be influential in promoting peace and unity. Their communication efforts can disseminate messages of tolerance and discourage violence. The research of Adebayo and Owoye (2017) highlights the role of religious leaders in mediating conflicts and fostering harmony, thus reducing insecurity. Examples are pastor, priest, imman, prophet, and pope. The role of communication in insecurity reduction is vital in addressing and mitigating security threats within society. Effective communication strategies play a significant role in preventing and responding to acts of insecurity (Ibe et al., n.d.; Ineji et al., 2018) The role of communication in insecurity reduction cannot be overlooked; it's a means to disseminate vital information related to security threats, preventive measures, and emergency responses Timely and accurate information can empower individuals and communities to take necessary precautions, report suspicious activities, and collaborate with security agencies, communication also plays a crucial role in creating awareness and educating the public about security risks, crime prevention techniques, and safety measures. This helps individuals become more proactive in safeguarding themselves and their communities. Effective communication fosters trust and cooperation between security agencies, community leaders, and citizens; transparent and open communication channels

encourage sharing of information, concerns, and feedback, strengthening collaborative efforts in addressing insecurity (McMahon, 2016).

Communication helps mobilize individuals and communities to actively engage in neighbourhood watch programmes, report suspicious activities, and support law enforcement efforts. Crisis and Emergency Communication: During crises, clear and effective communication is crucial for providing guidance, updates, and instructions to the public (Zakiri, 2020; Stavros, et al., 2023). Communication systems and protocols should be in place to swiftly convey important information to ensure public safety and facilitate emergency responses. Communication also fosters collaboration between public and private entities in addressing insecurity, and this can involve partnerships between government agencies, businesses, non-governmental organizations, and community-based organizations to share resources, expertise, and information for effective security measures (Servaes, 2013).

Also, through communication, various media platforms can shape public opinion, raise awareness, and influence behaviour regarding security issues. Responsible reporting and accurate portrayal of security incidents are essential in preventing panic and promoting informed decision-making. Effective communication systems also incorporate feedback mechanisms that allow individuals to report concerns, provide information, and offer suggestions for improving security measures, this two-way communication ensures that the needs and perspectives of the public are considered in security planning and implementation (Cornelissen, 2017).

The Ekiti government has made efforts to combat insecurity through law enforcement agencies and military operations. However, these measures alone have not been sufficient to reduce insecurity significantly. One critical aspect that has often been overlooked is the effective participation of stakeholders in the communication process. Communication plays a vital role in addressing insecurity by enhancing coordination, information sharing, and fostering trust between different actors involved. Thus, understanding and harnessing the potential of stakeholders' participation in communication usage is crucial for reducing insecurity in Ekiti state, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study is to explore the role of selected stakeholders in communication usage for the reduction of insecurity in Oye-Ekiti. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Analyze the role of government agencies as stakeholders to use effective communication in reducing insecurity.
- ii. Examine the impact of law enforcement authorities as stakeholders on using effective communication to address insecurity.
- iii. Explore the role of civil society organizations (CSOs) as stakeholders in using effective communication to promote transparency and accountability in security matters.

Justification for the study

Accessible literature evidence has revealed that none of the previous works on stakeholders' involvement in insecurity reduction has touched Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. Smith and Johnson (2018) inspected the effect of partner engagement on a community security data program in Florida. This report highlights the benefits of including partners such as law enforcement offices, community organizations, and the open in planning and actualizing communication procedures to decrease wrongdoing and improve social security. Muleta and Chigunta (2020) considered community interest in security administration in casual settlements in Ethiopia and highlighted the significance of comprehensive and participatory communication forms to progress security and advance social cohesion. Njoroge and Haynes (2017) inspected the part of citizens in community policing programmes in Kenya and found the significance of communication and collaboration between partners for effective security administration.

Lubbe and Reddy (2020) look at community endeavours to anticipate savage radicalism in South Africa and highlight that the community should create comprehensive communication methodologies and strategies to engage those who make an effect and construct beliefs. Emeka et

al. (2023) considered the utilization of unused media to spread negative messages in South-Eastern Nigeria and found that 51.0% of the respondents had experienced negative messages in most of the modern data. It was also uncovered that a normal of 74.8% (N=367) of the populace in South-South Nigeria utilized social media to freely express their sentiments. The present study may or may not garner such support in the usage of communication strategies to reduce insecurity in Ekiti state. Kees et al (2022) investigated the potential for neighbourhood partner association in emergency administration: and recognized the potential for collaboration between formal and conventional reaction organizations and neighbourhood partners to reply to issues, fortifying the relationship between the conclusion leads to a coordinated approach and capacity to manage issues. Johnstone and William (2015) inquired about viable communication methodologies for partner engagement and found that formal gatherings permit administration groups to define methodologies, make choices, and actualise exercises and ventures in which partners play a vital part in not being rejected.

Theoretical Framework

This study used the Systems Theory. System Theory was developed by Ludwig Von Bertalanffy (1968), a biologist who originated from life sciences, explaining the inter-relationship between organisms within the eco-system as a whole and unified system. Hence, nothing exists without other elements in the ecosystem. It has also been applied in other fields, including the area of communication, to explain the connectedness of various elements within the communication ecosystem, which includes social institutions, processes of communication, and information systems, amongst others (Morolake, 2017). For this study, the systems theory explains the relationship between the stakeholders such as government agencies, Civil Society Organizations and law enforcement authorities, their process of communication usage and national security, giving a holistic view of the connectedness of all the elements. Therefore, none of these stakeholders are isolated from each other as they all play a role in insecurity reduction as communication in various social institutions within the society can negatively or positively impact the security of the nation. The systems within a nation also evolve; the media systems within nations are evolving to accommodate citizen journalism since the advent of social media; governments within nations are also finding ways to be present on social media.

Method

This study adopts a quantitative research design approach with the use of primary sources of data involving a descriptive survey design to examine stakeholders' participation in communication usage for the reduction of insecurity in Oye LGA, Nigeria. Kumar (2014) states that quantitative methodology is used to answer questions about descriptions among measured variables to explain, predict, and control phenomena. The choice of Oye LGA for the study was informed by an increase in robbery attacks on banks, kidnapping activities, herders' crises, and brutality of all kinds.

The target population of this study consists of all the one hundred and fifty-one (151) stakeholders in the Oye local government, the population size was gathered from the local government secretariat: community leaders 17, registered local businesses 31, law enforcement 71, government agencies 11, and registered civil society 21 totaling 151 (Local Government Peace Building and Development Unit, 2023). The reason for the choice of this population was based on their previous involvement in security matters of the area under study, which put them in the best position to supply the needed data for the study.

A combination of purposive and stratified random sampling techniques was employed as follows:

1. Purposive sampling was used to select key stakeholders who possess significant knowledge and expertise in the field of insecurity reduction and communication strategies.

2. Stratified random sampling was used to ensure the representation of different stakeholders in the groups. The population was stratified based on stakeholder categories, such as government officials, security agencies, community leaders, civil society organizations, and citizens. Ten respondents each were selected from each stakeholder’s category, which summed up to 50 (33%) respondents in total. The choice of 10 respondents from each stratum was to ensure a fair representation of the sample for the study. The use of a 33% sample size was justified by Creswell and Creswell (2018), who stated that 20% to 50% can be appropriate for a small population of hundreds.

Data was collected through a self-structured questionnaire survey titled Stakeholders Participation in Communication Usage for Insecurity Reduction (SPCUIR) and administered to the selected stakeholders. The questionnaire was a four-point scale with response mode of Strongly Agree (SA) =4, Agree (A) =3, Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) =1. The choice of a self-structured questionnaire is based on its effectiveness in the data collection procedure, which achieves a high cooperation rate, especially among teenagers.

The three experts facially and contextually validated SPCUIR. Two were from the Department of Peace and Conflict Resolution, while one expert was drawn from the Measurement and Evaluation Department, all from Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti state. This ensures the content and facial validity of the instrument and helps obtain population generalizability and/or ensure the appropriateness of the content of the instrument. The questionnaire included items related to stakeholder engagement, communication channels, perceptions of effectiveness, and barriers to participation.

The researchers administered and retrieved instruments from the respondents in their various locations within Oye LGA within one month. Fifty (50) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to 50 respondents selected for the study with strict supervision. Due to caution and strict monitoring by the researchers, a 100 per cent return rate was actualised

The collected data was analysed using descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, which were employed to summarize and summarise the responses of the participants. The choice of mean and standard deviation was because the study is anchored on descriptive research designs, which typically require only descriptive statistics to facilitate the easier understanding of data supplied by the respondents on the role of selected stakeholders in communication usage for the reduction of insecurity in Oye LGA, Ekiti State. Mean, and standard deviation make the analysis easier for the reader to have a good understanding of the sample that understands the sample the study was conducted (Cresswell, 2018). Ethical considerations were collected from the local government headquarters and adhered to throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring their voluntary participation and the protection of their privacy and confidentiality. The study complied with relevant ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects.

Results and Discussion

This section dealt with the analysis, presentation and interpretation of results obtained from 50 stakeholders involved in the use of communication to reduce insecurity in Oye LGA.

Research Question one: What are the roles of government agencies as stakeholders to use effective communication in reducing insecurity?

Table 1: Analysis of Mean and Standard deviation of the Responses on roles of government agencies as stakeholders to use effective communication in reducing insecurity

S/N	Items	Mean	SA	Decision
1	Government agencies actively participate in implementing security measures to reduce insecurity in Oye Ekiti .	3.48	0.50	A

2	Government agencies effectively communicate security information to the public to create awareness and prevent insecurity.	3.54	0.51	SA
3	Government agencies collaborate with other stakeholders to coordinate efforts and address security challenges in Oye Ekiti	3.40	0.49	A
4	Government agencies take responsibility for developing and implementing policies that contribute to the reduction of insecurity in Oye Ekiti .	3.36	0.48	A
5	Government agencies play a leadership role in mobilizing resources and manpower to tackle insecurity effectively in Oye Ekiti	3.34	0.47	A

N₁=50 respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 above explores the perceived roles of government agencies in reducing insecurity. The entire results show exclusive acceptance of the items. This means that there was a strong collaboration among government agencies as stakeholders to use effective communication in reducing insecurity in Ekiti state.

Research Question two: What are impacts of law enforcement authorities as stakeholders to use effective communication in addressing insecurity?

Table 2: Analysis of Mean and Standard Deviation on the impacts of law enforcement authorities as stakeholders to use effective communication in addressing insecurity

S/N	Item	Mean	SA	Decision
6	Law enforcement authorities effectively respond to messages on security incidents and emergencies in Oye Ekiti .	3.22	0.41	A
7	Law enforcement authorities collaborate with other stakeholders to gather intelligence and prevent security threats in Oye Ekiti through effective communication	3.32	0.47	A
8	Law enforcement authorities actively engage with communities to build strong relationships and foster a sense of security in Oye Ekiti .	3.82	0.38	SA

N₂=50 respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 assesses the perceived impacts of law enforcement authorities in addressing insecurity: The results of the analysis show acceptance in its entirety. The acceptance of the entire items indicates a generally positive perception of their responsiveness to security incidents using effective communication. The analysis reveals that the law enforcement authorities as stakeholders use effective communication in addressing insecurity problems in Ekiti state.

Research Question three: what are the roles of civil society organizations (CSOs) as stakeholders to use effective communication in promoting transparency and accountability in security matters?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on the roles of civil society organizations (CSOs) as stakeholders to use effective communication in promoting transparency and accountability in security matters

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
9	Civil society organisations(CSOs) actively advocate for transparency and accountability in security operations and policies in Oye Ekiti .	3.92	0.27	SA
10	Civil society organisations (CSOs) effectively monitor and evaluate security initiatives to ensure transparency and accountability in Oye Ekiti .	3.60	0.49	SA
11	Civil society organizations (CSOs) actively engage in dialogue with government agencies and law enforcement authorities to promote transparency in security matters in Oye Ekiti .	3.58	0.49	SA
12	Civil society organizations (CSOs) provide platforms and opportunities for public participation and input in security-related decision-making processes in Oye Ekiti .	3.70	0.46	SA
13	Civil society organizations (CSOs) collaborate with other stakeholders to advocate for policies and practices that enhance transparency and accountability in security matters in Oye Ekiti .	3.80	0.40	SA

N₃=50 respondents

Table 3 explores the roles of civil society organizations (CSOs) as stakeholders in using effective communication to promote transparency and accountability in security matters: The analysis unveiled the acceptance of entire items of the questionnaire. This action revealed that CSOs as stakeholders use effective communication in promoting transparency and accountability in security issues. The result underscores their role in promoting a more open and accountable security landscape.

Discussion of Findings

Government Agencies and Security Reduction

The findings revealed that government agencies as stakeholders use effective communication to significantly reduce insecurity in Oye Ekiti. This finding implies that government depends on the power of effective communication to reduce insecurity in society. The finding is upheld by Nwankwo et al. (2023), who stated that Nigerians depend so much on mass media for accurate and timely information about the happenings in society. This finding is an embodiment of Aliyu (2023) who discovered that an effective information security strategy would be the best

measure to adopt by government agencies to tackle the insecurity challenges faced by Nigeria which also obstructs its potential to drive sustainable national security and development. Overall, these findings underscore the multifaceted role of government agencies in orchestrating security efforts and their significance in addressing insecurity in Oye Ekiti.

It was opined by government agencies that a notable majority agree that these agencies actively implement security measures; this indicates a perceived commitment to enhancing security within the community. This finding aligns with Omoroje et al. (2020) who found that government agencies actively participate in implementing security measures to reduce insecurity.

Moreover, effective communication of security information by government agencies is also acknowledged, suggesting their efforts in raising public awareness. This implies that the adoption of timely communication by government agencies assists the public in taking proactive measures to tackle security issues. The finding is corroborated by Kumafan (2024) who realized a call to action for policymakers, statisticians, and stakeholders to prioritize ethics and proactive communication as fundamental pillars of the Nigerian Statistical System NSS and security issues.

It was also noted that collaboration emerges as a key aspect, with a substantial percentage agreeing that government agencies work with other stakeholders to address security challenges. This underscores the importance of coordinated efforts for effective security management. This finding agrees with Mohammed et al (2019) who recommended that the Government should design a unified policy blueprint for interagency joint operation purposes and a central intelligence gathering data bank for the security agencies.

The data further emphasizes the responsibility of government agencies in policy formulation, with a significant proportion agreeing that these agencies take charge of developing and implementing policies to reduce insecurity. This highlights the role of authorities in shaping the security framework. This is corroborated by Tobias (2017) that government agencies are suitable for developing and implementing policies regarding security within their jurisdiction.

It was equally opined that government agencies play a leadership role in mobilizing resources and manpower to tackle insecurity effectively. The findings align with Abdullahi (2020) who found that government agencies are seen as leaders in resource mobilization for security initiatives, this leadership role is crucial in ensuring the availability of necessary resources to combat insecurity effectively.

Law Enforcement Authorities and Insecurity Reduction

The finding also revealed that law enforcement authorities as stakeholders use effective communication in addressing insecurity problems in Ekiti state. This implies that law enforcement agencies play vital roles in insecurity reduction. The implication of this finding to society is that citizens of a free society will live freely and attract more development. This finding is supported by Emmanuel (2019) who noted that ensuring the safety and security of the citizenry is primarily the responsibility of the state through the effort of the law enforcement agencies through their effective and efficient discharge of duties.

It was opined by respondents that law enforcement agencies play a significant role in effectively responding to messages on security incidents and emergencies. This is in agreement with Obarisiagbon and Akintoye (2019) who averred that there is a need to strengthen the security and judicial system in Nigeria to respond to security incidents and emergencies actively. This recognition reflects the importance of swift and effective response in maintaining public safety and order.

Collaboration emerges as a strong theme, with a substantial majority agreeing that law enforcement authorities collaborate with stakeholders to gather intelligence and prevent security threats. This emphasizes the value of shared information and coordination among various entities to thwart potential threats. The finding is in agreement with Smith and Johnson (2018) who found that engaging stakeholders in community safety communication is a crucial way of a crime

prevention initiative. The findings also underscore the significance of law enforcement's interaction with the community.

It was also opined that law enforcement authorities actively engage with communities to build strong relationships, fostering a sense of security. This engagement highlights the role of law enforcement in enhancing public trust and cooperation, thereby contributing to a safer environment. The finding is contrary to Emmanuel (2019) and Obarisiagbon and Akintoye (2019) who found that the roles and responsibilities of law enforcement agencies were hampered by large “ungoverned space” which Boko Haram insurgents group and other criminal groups take advantage of in perpetrating various crimes and criminality.

Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and Insecurity Reduction

The finding revealed that CSOs as stakeholders use effective communication in promoting transparency and accountability in security issues. This implies that CSOs depend on the use of effective communication to promote transparency and accountability in governance, especially in issues related to security problems. Muhammed and Abdulkarim (2017) substantiated this finding that there is little or no restriction on civil society to organize itself through the formation of non-governmental organizations or civil society organizations or coalitions to agitate for accountability and transparency in governance. Such roles of CSOs can be viewed from dimensions such as: Improving the quality of governance, developing the capacity of governments to apply the principles of accountability, transparency and openness; and working towards gaining the commitment of all elected officials, public servants, and NGOs in all facets of governance including security issues. Chukwuemeka (2016) found that Civil Society Organizations complement the government's efforts in peace and security; and political leadership across the world. The researcher adds that CSOs prevent and resolve conflicts because of their in-depth knowledge of context and expertise in working closely with communities.

It was opined that CSOs actively advocate for transparency and accountability in security operations and policies. This suggests a recognized role for CSOs in holding security stakeholders accountable. The finding is heightened by Omede and Bakare (2014) who recommend that Civil Society groups need to be sanitized and strengthened to ensure effective service delivery through the advent of permitting surroundings for their operation and they must preserve an excessive diploma of independence from the government. Muhammad and Abdulkarim (2017) and Popoola and Alao (2017) substantiate the finding when revealed that, the existence of civil society organizations greatly contributes to promoting democracy and good governance in Nigeria and recommended that the government at all levels should encourage citizens, especially youths to actively participate in CSO sports and make applicable CSOs in coverage formulation, implementation, tracking and supervision, in addition to different decision-making processes.

The respondent also shows that Civil Society Organizations are seen as effective monitors of security initiatives, reflecting their watchdog function in ensuring responsible security practices. This finding on effective monitors of security initiatives was supported by Osayekemwen and Adeoluwa (2022) and Dawit (2023) who show the state's increasing interest in the activities of CSOs on the grounds of national security was highly imperative.

Furthermore, the respondents pointed out that there was an active engagement of CSOs with government agencies and law enforcement authorities, highlighting their role as intermediaries for dialogue and collaboration. Hansson, Håkansson, and Wangel (2018) substantiated this finding, averred that CSOs are also recognized for providing platforms for public participation in security-related decision-making, emphasizing their contribution to inclusive security governance. The data

in above table 3 buttressed this finding when underscores CSOs' collaborative advocacy for transparent policies and practices, indicating their active role in shaping security policies.

Conclusion

The study underscored the intricate web of stakeholders actively engaged in reducing insecurity in Oye Ekiti. Each stakeholder group contributes distinctively to the multifaceted landscape of security enhancement. The collaborations, roles, and responsibilities of these entities play a pivotal role in building a safer community.

Limitations of the Study

Although the research provides valuable information, there are acknowledged limitations. Findings are based on perception, which may not always accurately reflect actual performance. Additionally, the fact that the study was conducted in a specific area (Oye Ekiti) may limit the generalizability of the results.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, several recommendations were proposed:

1. Stakeholders should prioritize collaborative efforts, fostering partnerships that leverage collective resources and expertise in the usage of communication for insecurity reduction in Ekiti state, Nigeria.
2. The government should encourage increased community engagement through community policing initiatives and programmes that empower residents to be proactive in the usage of communication channels to report security concerns. This strategy will reduce insecurity in Ekiti state, Nigeria.
3. Civil Society Organizations should advocate more for enhanced transparency and accountability across stakeholder groups, ensuring that information sharing is prioritized.
4. Government should support capacity-building programmes for law enforcement to strengthen their roles in security efforts. Such programmes increase the competencies of these agencies in communication usage for insecurity reduction in Nigeria.

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